

Node Mobility Optimization in Multi-hop WBAN Using Genetic Algorithm

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Abstract— Wireless Body Area Network (WBAN) is an uprising innovation for short-range remote communication inside, on or circular the body, within the fundamental for therapeutic applications. In this paper, an adjuvant scheme has been proposed to increase the node mobility in WBAN. Dead nodes, path loss, low residual energy, and less throughput are the main causes for decreasing mobility of nodes. A comparative study has been done between the existing and proposed multi-hop protocol using the Genetic Algorithm and Fuzzy logic. This proposed model has been simulated in MATLAB simulator.

Keywords—WBAN, Node Mobility, Genetic Algorithm, Fuzzy logic.6

I. INTRODUCTION

WBAN as a facilitator and information collector, for the reason of real-time checking of patients' physiological parameters, such as ECG, EEG, blood weight and so forward. With the aging of the individuals, remaining therapeutic assets cannot delight future healthcare stresses of seniors and patients. Assets are lacking and it is incomprehensible for most noteworthy patients to oversee to pay for long-term clinic breaks due to money-related confinements, work, and other points of interest, indeed even though their health ion must be checked in a real-time [1] or brief discontinuous time mode. the result, remote observing restorative plans will get to be a portion of versatile healthcare middles with real-time nursing within the future. In WBANs, sensor nodes are worked with constrained vitality sources. It is required to utilize the least control for transmitting information from sensor nodes to the sink. One of the major impediments in WBAN is to energize the batteries. An efficient directing convention is required to overcome this issue of energizing batteries. Depending on QoS parameters a therapeutic master will give the command to enact appropriate activity in case circumstance isn't ordinary. In WBAN, different remote communication innovations like Zigbee, Bluetooth, 2.4 GHz ISM band, and Intra-body communication are conveyed to exchange the information between all the sensors and facilitator hub [2]. But in WBAN not at all like WSN, there is the number of impediments like battery control, scope run, receiving wire stature of the handset, heterogeneous exchange rates, tall flag weakening, etc. [2] But transmission with tall QoS parameters like least impedances, tall bundle conveyance proportion (PDR), tall throughput, least, expended vitality, low idleness, tall connect unwavering quality, etc. is the extreme prerequisite due to their application fields. A few creators have distinguished the alternative network which known as follows:

(a) Simply get to and consolation [3]: WBAN nodes are put on the patient body surface or are covered beneath their cloth. Little estimates and low taken a toll are required.

(b) Real-time preparing [1]: Body Area Network is utilized, enlisting patient physiological exercises, activities, which may happen proper schedule [3, 4]. Its necessity directed to its applications which exchanged made strides unwavering quality and vitality utilization.

(c) Portability demands [3]: In this network, clients have free mobility. Hence, the nodes shared by the same portability design regarded the outside door. These body sensors given successfully handled by the central sink.

In this paper, our target is to optimize the node mobility of WBAN. WBAN nodes use a limited energy source to keep nodes alive for a long time. Node mobility always increases the performance of WBANs whereas long-distance route decreases throughput. By using the multi-hop node protocol moving distance between nodes can reduce the path. In this paper our goals are:

- ❖ To minimize the dead nodes
- ❖ To increase the residual energy
- ❖ To reduce the path loss
- ❖ To increase the throughput
- ❖ To determine the suitable path for next node selection

II. WBAN CHARACTERISTICS

WBAN is used mainly in the medical sector to observe the patient's condition. WBAN network is used in the human or animal body by placing tiny Bio-Medical-sensor nodes [5]. Network sensor nodes send all the data to the sink to transmit to authority or doctor. This network is used to provide the best services to patients from a long distance. Nowadays WBAN system is used by general peoples for monitoring their health condition by wearable devices like a smartwatch, smart shoes, digital glasses, etc. Day by day exercises like running and walking and physiological exercises just like the pulse and respiratory have an impact on the remote engendering significantly [6][7].

2.1.1 A typical WBAN scheme contains

- ❖ A small networks around the body

- ❖ A sink connecting to a different kind of network which will be another node with routing and data mixture options
- ❖ An organization like website or computing setup
- ❖ Software for health care authority to give better services

Figure-1: A typical WBAN architecture.

III. RELATED WORKS

In the paper Blumrosen Et Al. [8] Body sensors need to be small, lightweight, noninvasive, and wireless-enabled and must consume low power when operational. The batteries can be effectively changeable by the patient own or medical Authority, the sensor will be still operational when the batteries have low energy. A WSN will be a comfortable wear for a patient and anyone can change without professional skill and no need to implement proper position. When conductive equipment is made with organic e-textiles and wireless-enabled technology.

Saleem Et AL. [9] and Kumar and Lee [10] identified some attacks that can be dangerous to the remote medical system at MAC, the physical and transport layer. Different types of medical equipment have different types of data rate capabilities, so the network needs enough bandwidth to support the whole operation and needs the best network protocols. Sensing, processing, transceiver, and power these four small components are used to make up a sensor node. The transceiver used the most power in the sensor node. To reduce the power consumption all the nodes must be used as autonomous operation. Multi-path can reduce power consumption. From the other viewpoint, WBANs must be highly secured to protect personal data and medical data. To collect sensitive data and utilize them in a secure system used a high algorithm to protect from dangerous Trojan attacks, to protect from hackers.

From all previous discussions, WBANs need tiny wireless WSN nodes around or in the body, quick real-time processing [3,4]. The nodes are will be flexible and easy to use by patients. The consumption will not be critical if the batteries are easy to changeable. Dependability, mobility, and data encryption must be support by WBANs.

IV. PROPOSED METHOD

WBANs can impressively spare costs and time for each healthcare experts and patients since of the quality of patients and situation independent recognition. A parcel of as of late, the capacity administration downside has been tended to victimization hypothesis of recreations, for the occasion, in CDMA systems and conveyed systems Remote dispersed miniaturized scale sensor frameworks can modify blame

tolerant recognition and administration of a run of applications.

In the present Holter Monitory system shown in figure 2, which combines with lots of wire and it is not even user friendly. Also, the Battery backup only 24hours which is another drawback of the device.

Figure-2: Present monitoring system

Additionally, a few WBAN structures have been effectively tried, particularly in health monitoring uses. In these structures, the Wireless sensor nodes put over body surface could be a smart phone or a personal digital assistant (PDA) which can work as a transceiver and operated by human. In these types of situation, the PDA acts as a sink hub; this is a portion of the WBAN can connect to the healthcare center by Any cellular networks such as GSM, CDMA,EDGE, WCDMA, Portable WiMAX, or other wireless technologies.

Figure-3: Mobility-free WBAN architecture approach.

To increase the mobility of WBAN these types of connectivity are very crucial. Figure 3 presents the modern methodology of mobility-free WBAN engineering. At WBAN part sensor nodes are implanted over human body and connect the application part with any mobile technology. It can support stationary or mobile modes both. It can be implemented with other application without any resources on WBAN. In this research [11], the authors prove the potential of using RSSI capacities on the kinematic human body. Figure 4 shows the Flowchart of the proposed model. In this flowchart first WBAN Testbed area needs to be selected. Then the nodes will be initialized with their coverages. After that source and destination path will be determined and

Genetic Algorithm (GA) will be initiated to ensure the optimal route. After that, Function's fitness will be checked according to Fuzzy Logic.

Figure-4: Flowchart of the proposed model.

This Proposed method would be user-friendly and it will reduce in-hospital stays that can reduce waste of time. Another important point can be noted here that continuous monitoring may help in early detection which may prevent from falling into critical situation in a short span of time.

WBANs are application-dependent, being by and large categorized into two kinds: (i) event discovery and (ii) periodic result. Within the to begin with, the nodes send information as it were when an event happens whereas within the moment the nodes send information at intermittent intervals. An individual instance of the organized topology, both the nodes' resources and the information sent are diverse. One of the foremost critical things in planning measures for WBANs is adjusting of QoS imperatives with low power control limitations of nodes. A few standards have been adopted for medical sector applications like Bluetooth (IEEE 802.15.1) or ZigBee (IEEE 802.15.4) protocols. These remote standards are well archived and tried but are not well-organized cause the target systems that are more adaptable and are utilized for longer transmission areas. This makes them less energy productive than protocols that are particularly architecture for a WBAN (e.g., 802.15.6) [12].

V. SIMULATION AND ANALYSIS

This investigation has been conducted by using GA (Genetic algorithm) for the optimization of node mobility in WBAN.

Here Sensor Node Classification (SNC) scheme has been performed. Genetic algorithm, also known as a global heuristic algorithm, which estimates an optimal solution through generating different individuals. It mainly performs three steps for checking i.e., Mutation, Crossover, and Genesis. The first step mutation is used for conserving and introducing diversity in GA. It is a genetic operator, which maintains genetic diversity from one generation of a population of genetic algorithm chromosomes to the next. In the next step crossover is applied which mainly used for the matching [13]. In our proposed model algorithm, this is the most important part. Only the trusted nodes will be passes through the next step for fitness check. Genesis is the concluding component of GA which is used for mutation and crossover formula in the programming section [13]. This methodology can be operated in training which trains the input pattern and testing which is used to test the individual nodes in WBAN network. The classification is done by using Fuzzy logic. The work is being tried on parameters such as network lifetime, throughput, BER (Bit error rate), path loss, and residual energy, etc.

The following are the steps that illustrate the proposed model that has to be finished.

Step 1: Design WBAN by space of height and dimension of 100×100.

Step 2: Initialize the detector nodes within the WBAN. Within the planned work, we tend to implement fifty varieties of detector nodes.

Step 3: The WBAN coverage space is initialized by utilizing the supply node and destination node within the WBAN.

Step 4: With the routing protocol, the route is being discovered by the info transmission of the supply node towards the destination node.

Step 5: For optimizing the route, the simplest route optimization algorithmic program named as a genetic algorithmic program is applied.

Step 6: If the GA fitness performs is true as per the symbolic logic rule set then a unique route is developed between supply and destination otherwise the node is rejected and checks another node within the WBAN.

Step 7: A supreme test is made among supply and goal, the execution measurements like vitality utilization, bit blunder rate, throughput, and delay inside the arrangement have been measured.

Throughput: It is named as the total number of packet send within the recreation time. It can be clarified numerically as [14]:

$$\text{Throughput} = \frac{\sum \text{Packets sent}}{\text{Total data packets}}$$

BER (Bit Error rate): BER is characterized as the number of bits transmitted per unit time [15].

$$BER = \frac{\text{Bit errors}}{\text{total number of transferred bit during an interval}}$$

Energy Utilization: Vitality utilization is named as the full vitality being exchanged by each hub in WBAN at changed arrange layers. It is characterized scientifically as underneath:
 $n-1$

$$\text{Energy Consumption} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} (\text{Energy_consumed_by_node})$$

End to end delay within the numerical term is characterized as the overall time being slipped by for the bundle information transmission.

$$\text{Dend-end} = \text{Dtrans} + \text{Dprop} + \text{Dproc}$$

Where Dend-end= End-To-End Delay

Dtrans= Transmission Delay

Dprop= Propagation

Delay Dproc= Processing Delay

VI. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In our paper mesh topology has been considered to deploy the sensor network. Mesh topology provides robustness, short path selection, high data transferring rate.

Figure-5: Deployment of sensor nodes.

Figure-5 shows the deployment of sensor nodes in WBAN. This deployment is simulated in MATLAB and considering the number of nodes is 8 where 6 are active nodes and 2 dead nodes. The green circles are considered as active node and the red circles denote the dead nodes. We analyzed the WBAN network using MULTI-HOP and showed the performance graphs of path loss, residual energy, packets received at the sink by using 8 nodes in Figures 5, 6, 7, and 8.

Figure-6: Analysis of network lifetime.

Figure-7: Analysis of throughput

Figure-8: Analysis of residual energy

Figure-9: Path loss

Proposed Fuzzy Logic for Node Mobility:

We considered 3 main network nodes and 3 sub-nodes each of them. We put different values for different ranges for those all nodes. In Fuzzy logic, we have set rules in the Mamdani rule box. By setting individual rules for each node we have distributed a specific range for the system. The output shows the surfaces between two nodes concerning those rules.

Figure-10: Adding 3 Main nodes, Mamdani rule scope, and output scope.

Figure 10 shows three example nodes and output scope for Mobility analysis. Three nodes have different ranges. After adding rules in the Mamdani rule box. A node can define the best path for forwarding nodes which can increase mobility.

Figure-11: Created simulation rules in Fuzzy logic

Figure-12: Created simulation rules in Fuzzy logic.

Figure 12 shows the rules which are created in the Mamdani rule box. Here the ranges are, node-1=2.5, node-2=7.5 and node-3=12.5. Figures 11,12 and 13 show the surface graphs of 3 nodes.

Figure-13: Surface graph of node 2, 1.

Figure-14: Surface graph of node 3, 2

Figure-15: Surface graph of Node-3, 1

Our observation from this work is to increase the time of alive nodes in Multi-hop. It also increases throughput to transmit

higher data to the sink. This topology decreases the energy drain and pathloss for a short link. On the other hand, in the Mamdani-Fuzzy logic technique, we can create our own oriented rules for the distribution of nodes and determine the best path for transmission in WBAN. By using this technique WBAN gets low power consumption, minimized dead node, and overlapping. Without the Fuzzy logic technique, we can't easily get the data transfer path or next node selection for WBAN.

Figure-16: Comparison of nodes lifetime between Existing and Proposed WBAN.

From node mobility analysis we observed some improvement in WBAN. Figure 16 shows the comparison of nodes lifetime between existing and proposed WBAN. Here multihop protocol reduces the node forwarding path. We can conclude that here increased the nodes' lifetime by 13.13%.

Figure-17: Comparison of residual energy between Existing and Proposed WBAN.

Figure 17 shows the comparison of residual energy between existing and proposed WBAN. For reducing the node forwarding path the energy abstains from consumption. Here we can conclude that the residual energy increased by 8.87% than before.

Figure-18: Comparison of path loss between Existing and Proposed WBAN.

In figure-18 the comparison of path loss between existing and proposed WBAN is shown. Here we observed that the path loss decreased in the proposed protocol. So we can conclude that the path loss decreased by 17.53%.

Figure-19: Comparison of throughput between Existing and Proposed WBAN.

Figure-19 shows the comparison of throughput between existing and proposed WBAN. Here increased throughput by 47.11%.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a Genetic Algorithm in the field of WBAN using a multi-hop protocol. WBAN framework is introduced in clinics and the framework could be three-level engineering which comprises of Medical Server, Individual Server, Sensor nodes and all levels have it possess usefulness to total the method of WBAN. Specialists utilizing their gadgets with the assistance of the web can check their patients and indeed the patients who are being introduced with sensors moreover require web networks in their gadgets like portable phones, PDAs, etc. Simulation results have shown the effectiveness of the proposed model. Using multi-hop rule in GA gave the best possible route among various possible routes in the shortest period. It also improved Throughput, Packet delivery ratio, Residual energy consumed by nodes, and increased network lifetime. In the future, within the WBAN frameworks which are introduced in clinics require security which is the major issue nowadays. Security issues like confirmation, patient's e-reports that are spared within the cloud database is to be moved forward by utilizing any best optimization method. Patients don't need to uncover their individual life's issues with any obscure individual. On the off chance that the persistent who is having any inveterate infection like Asthma, Alzheimer illness, Helps, Cancer or any other infection which he/she don't want to talk about with any other, so there's the zone where security is the major concern

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